

Number of replicates in the analyses (after outlier removal).

Transition	BR transition					RB transition				
Time point	Ctl	12h	24h	48h	96	Ctl	12h	24h	48h	96h
Number of replicates	4	8	8	8	8	4	8	8	8	8